

THE EFFECT OF PRODUCT DIVERSIFICATION ON THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This article explores the features of the development of industrial enterprises, their current state today, as well as the influence of the diversification factor on the results of production. The author makes reflections on the development of the country's economy, improving the economic results of the industry and improving economic efficiency.

Keywords: Industry, company, efficiency, production, valuation, diversification, stock return, capital return, profitability, modernization.

Introduction. Development of industrial enterprises is the main task today. Political and economic aspirations and economic integration of countries are expressed on the basis of industry.

The development of the industrial network directly depends on the geography of the market of industrial products, and overall economic efficiency is ensured on the basis of improving the sale of products. The products of the country's industrial enterprises are in demand among buyers in the domestic and foreign markets and are entering new consumer markets. In 2022, the country's export volume will be 19.2 billion. amounting to soums and increased by 16.3% compared to last year. The main share of exports corresponded to industrial products and reached 26.1%. The export of textiles, non-ferrous metals, iron and steel metals increased by 7.2% compared to last year, that is, the geography of export of products will be more than 70 countries in 2022. Nevertheless, it is necessary to further increase the above indicators based on the effective use of existing production resources [1]. For this, first of all, it is necessary to establish production in accordance with internal capabilities based on a deep study of the demand for industrial products.

Based on these tasks, it is necessary to make effective use of production opportunities, modernize production equipment, organize production in accordance with market demand, ensure competitiveness and increase labor productivity. In this case, it is of urgent scientific and practical importance to study the efficiency of industrial enterprises based on the assessment of their economic status in practice, to determine the factors affecting efficiency, and to study the impact of product diversification on the general economic efficiency.

Analysis and results. In the activities of industrial enterprises, the adoption of new types of production based on diversification, the introduction of new technologies and, based on this, are considered a factor that ensures economic efficiency, and this is directly influenced by internal and external factors.

Internal factors include the state of existing technologies, the level of utilization of production capacity, modernization of equipment, innovation, management, and the level of product quality.

External factors are based on the market factor, macroeconomic stability, changes in consumer demand, competition, economic policy of the state, geographical conditions and price policy.

There are different approaches to the impact of diversification on the level of economic efficiency in industrial enterprises, and a number of interpretations have been used in the research work.

A.V. Gladkiy [5], V.G. Shadrina [13], M.P. Narzikulov [9], D. Mamadjonov [8] and Sh.Sh. Shadmanov [12] describes macro-level factors affecting production efficiency as strategic directions, state of infrastructures, geographical location of enterprises, level of territorial development, diversification process and those who studied on the basis of specific features of proportional organization and development of production infrastructure.

Parakhina V.N., Voronova G.V., Momotova O.N. estimated that the diversification of enterprise activities directly depends on the location of production and the degree of specialization of regions based on the following formula [14].

$$D = \frac{d_{V_{RP}}^{otr}}{D_{V_{RP}}^{otr}} \quad (1)$$

In this:

D- level of diversification of the regional economy;

$d_{V_{RP}}^{otr}$ - the share of industry in the gross regional product (GDP);

$D_{V_{RP}}^{otr}$ –the share of foreign industry in the gross domestic product (GDP).

In many studies, V.S.Mkhitaryan, M.G.Polikarpova justified the high possibility of assessment based on the Herfindalya-Hirshmana index. The Herfindalya-Hirshmana index is used to evaluate market competition and is calculated based on the following formula [10].

$$HI = S_1^2 + S_2^2 + \dots + S_n^2 \quad (3)$$

Here: S_1, S_2 are the ratio of the volume of the company's sold products to the volume of total industrial products.

In the above studies, if the diversification of production was evaluated based on the branch and regional characteristics, the breadth of statistical data and their use cause inconvenience.

Although the presented methods are effective for use in the activities of enterprises, they cannot fully assess the efficiency of diversification of enterprises, but they can be used to estimate the overall diversification coefficient. In our opinion, when approaching diversification from the point of view of economic efficiency, determining this indicator based on the change in the volume of sold products will give a positive result. Therefore, the methodology for assessing the quantitative and qualitative level of diversification for industrial enterprises has been improved.

$$DE_t = \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) * \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{SQ_t^i}{Q_t^i} \right] - \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right) * \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{SQ_b^j}{Q_b^j} \right] \quad (4)$$

In this case: DE_t -diversification efficiency; n -the number of types of products produced by the enterprise during the period of diversification; m -the number of types of products produced in the initial state; SQ_t^i - is the volume of products sold after diversification; SQ_b^j -

volume of sold products in the period before diversification.

Based on the analysis of the considered methods, based on the above information, the evaluation of the efficiency of diversification in the assessment of the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises is an acceptable method.

Based on the above information, we will develop proposals and recommendations for increasing the economic efficiency of industrial enterprises based on the studied indicators and the use of methods for their determination.

The dynamics of production of textile products in Andijan region industry has changed somewhat. In particular, the share of textile products did not change during 2012-2014, it was equal to 14.6% in 2015 and 14.7% in 2021. The increase in the production volume of ready-made clothing products by industrial enterprises will be equal to 8.9% in 2022, which is 5.5 times more than in 2012 and 3.9 times more than in 2016.

Table 1

The share of textile and ready-made clothing products in total industrial products¹

Years	On textile products	On ready-made clothing product
2012-y.	8,5	1,6
2015-y.	11,2	2,0
2020-y.	7,7	5,5
2021-y.	8,3	5,8
2022-y.	14,7	8,9

Taking into account the high raw materials, material resources and labor resources of the region's economy, the development of resource-intensive enterprises (with high material resources and labor capacity) creates an opportunity to ensure economic growth. Therefore, it is necessary to diversify the production of textile industry enterprises in the region.

Based on the above information, it is necessary to produce competitive products on the basis of diversification and concentration of resources for the development of the industrial network in the region.

Based on the results of the conducted research, the following conclusions were reached based on the study of the results of the industrial enterprises of Andijan region:

Although the industrial sector is considered one of the leading sectors in the national economy, the economic opportunities of industrial enterprises in Andijan region are insufficient, because the state of raw resources, the level of utilization of production capacity, and the incomplete satisfaction of the demand for products hinder agricultural processing and construction enterprises. expresses the need for development;

In the location of industrial enterprises, taking into account the state of available resources, population location, infrastructure, regional characteristics and level

of specialization, locating enterprises that have a negative impact on the environment in less populated areas (Ulug'nor, Boston);

for the development of the industrial network, the possibilities of diversification of production were evaluated, taking into account the high impact of product consumption, available material and labor resources on the activity of textile enterprises.

Therefore, one of the main factors for improving the realization of products in enterprises is based on diversification. We study the economic efficiency of product diversification based on its cyclical characteristics. We analyze the effectiveness of diversification based on the above determination methodology (3).

$$DE_t = \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{7}\right) * \sum_{i=1}^7 \frac{QS_1^i + QS_2^i + \dots + QS_7^i}{Q_t^i} \right] - \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{5}\right) * \sum_{j=1}^5 \frac{QS_1^j + QS_2^j + \dots + QS_5^j}{Q_b^j} \right] =$$

$$= \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{7}\right) * \frac{964536,8}{999520,1} \right] - \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{5}\right) * \frac{291890,3}{317272,7} \right] =$$

$$= (0,857 * 0,965) - (0,8 * 0,92) = 0,091$$

In Skorton Textile LLC, this indicator was equal to 0.83 coefficient in 2022 and 0,74 coefficient in 2020. According to the above methodology, the difference is improved by 0.09 (or) 9.1 percent (Table 3).

¹ Data from Andijan Region Statistics Department.

Table 3

Diversification efficiency (coefficient) in some textile industrial enterprises in Andijan region ²				
№	Years	2021-y	2022-y	farq
1.	“Skorton tekstil” LLC	0,74	0,83	0,091
2.	“Saxovat Teks” LLC	0,79	0,87	0,083
3.	“Xo’jaobod turon tekstil” LLC	0,76	0,92	0,16

In "Sakhovat Teks" LLC, this indicator was equal to 0.87 coefficient in 2022 and 0.79 coefficient in 2021. As a result, diversification efficiency was 0.08 (8.3 percent), i.e., this indicator was equal to 0.16 coefficient in "Khojaabad Turon Textile" LLC.

Conclusions and offers. As a result of our research, it is of scientific and practical importance to study the diversification of the market of industrial products into the following groups

So, diversification of products in production is one of the resources that ensures the balanced development of not only the industrial sector, but also all sectors of our economy, that is:

- expansion of blood circulation;
- introducing new types of products into production;
- ensuring economic development based on marketing and innovative activities has a direct impact.

Therefore, there is a high possibility of mastering a new type of production, modernization of production equipment, supporting innovations and increasing the volume of products based on the diversification of textile products.

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² Author's development based on the information of "Skorton Textile" LLC, "Sakhavat Teks" LLC and "Khojaabad Turon Textile" LLC